

Annual General Meeting Conference 2022

The destroyed Drama Theater in Mariupol, Ukraine

17 SEPTEMBER 2022

The protection of Heritage in time of conflict

The destruction of cultural property in time of conflict is not a recent issue. Centuries of war, colonisation and industrialisation – among other ongoing processes – have caused the destruction and displacement of millions of people and objects. We continue to witness the destruction of heritage sites, the looting of archaeological and cultural objects, and the displacement of people due to cultural, political, and environmental causes across the world, including Syria, Iraq, Libya, Mali... and more recently in Ukraine.

Ukrainian archaeological heritage under threat of Russian aggression: problems and prospects

Military conflicts always cause irreparable damage to nature and culture, which is reflected in ecological and humanitarian disasters, the devaluation of human life, and the destruction of cultural heritage. The consequences of hostilities are particularly devastating for archaeological sites, given the non-restorability of archaeological layers, the inextricable connection of sites with the landscape and ecological environment, and the universal nature of the information that can be obtained during research.

Archaeological sites exist in an “unmanifested state” and the vast majority of them are not included in the lists of cultural heritage monuments. The

discovery of archaeological sites is often related to catastrophic events, and in this case – the destruction of landscapes because of military operations. Direct conducting of hostilities, the movement of soil during the construction of fortifications, damage due to rocket fire and bombing affects the state of sites’ preservation. The most significant, dominant formations of the historical landscape suffer the greatest damage due to the active use of convenient locations for the construction of modern fire and defense positions.

Among the serious challenges for Ukrainian archaeology are the use of archaeological sites as military objects,

illegal excavations in the occupied territories, looting of local museums, and increasing trade in archaeological objects. The question of monitoring the state of archaeological objects in the liberated territories requires significant organizational and legal foundations. As an additional and necessary requirement to the declared martial law, it is proposed to strengthen control over immovable and movable objects of archaeological heritage in Ukraine.

Vsevolod Ivakin is a graduate of the Faculty of History of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv (2000).

Since 1995 he works at the Institute of Archaeology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. In 2009, he defended his PhD thesis “The burial monuments of Old Russ Kiev”. He is teaching the archaeological course: “Old Rus and and its neighbors” (Department of Archaeology, Faculty of Humanities at the University “Kiev-Mohyla Academy”.

Dr Vsevolod Ivakin

Institute of Archaeology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine

— 14:00–14:15

Ukrainian archaeological heritage under threat of Russian aggression: problems and prospects (cont.)

Vsevolod Ivakin is the head of the department of Archaeology of Kyiv and chief of Architectural-archaeological Expedition which is engaged in rescue archaeological research in Kyiv and Kyiv region. Research interests: medieval and modern European archeology and history, funeral practice and necropoles, methods of preventive archaeological research, preservation of cultural heritage.

Vsevolod is also the founder of the scientific NGO “Hlib Ivakin Center for Medieval Studies”. From the beginning of the military aggression of the Russian Federation, Vsevolod became a head of Archaeological Monitoring Expedition of Institute of Archaeology NAS of Ukraine

in order to develop a monitoring process for archaeological sites damaged by the war.

Pavlo Shydlovskiy is a graduate of the Faculty of History of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv (1997).

He worked at the Institute of Archaeology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, the Kyiv Regional Center for the Protection of Monuments of History, Archaeology and Art, and the Scientific Research Institute for Monuments Preservation Studies. Since 2003, he has been teaching courses related to prehistoric archaeology at the Department of Archaeology and Museum

Studies of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. In 2008, he defended his PhD thesis 'Cultural adaptation of prehistoric hunters of Eastern Europe (18-10 ka BP)'.

In 2014, he received the academic title of associate professor. Pavlo Shydlovskiy is the head of the department's archaeological expedition, the focus of which is the study of the prehistoric sites of the Middle Dnieper region. The world-famous Upper Paleolithic Mezhyrich

settlement of mammoth hunters is of particular interest. Pavlo is also the founder of the scientific NGO Center for Paleoethological Studies and VITA ANTIQUA publishing. From the beginning of the military aggression of the Russian Federation, Pavlo took an active part in the Kaniv Territorial Defense Service, and became a member of the Ukrainian State Institute of Cultural Heritage in order to develop a monitoring process for archaeological sites damaged by the war.

Dr Pavlo Shydlovskiy

Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv
Ukrainian State Institute for Cultural Heritage

14:00–14:15

www.rescue-archaeology.org.uk

Programme by directionforward.com